

RESEARCH OF THE STRUCTURE OF POLYMER COMPOSITION

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Abstract: The paper studies the surface morphology of original polymers and polymer mixtures obtained on the basis of suspension polyvinyl chloride and ethylene vinyl acetate copolymer by scanning electron microscopy.

Keywords: study, Electron microscopy, surface morphology, PVC-C/SEVA.

Analysis of patent information, domestic and foreign literature allowed to say about the apparent insufficiency of information about two-component polymer mixtures of PVC-C/SEVA type. To eliminate this problem it is necessary to consider mechanisms of formation of mixtures of such polymers, to reveal conditions of formation of their structure and temperature ranges of working capacity. As a detailed study of the structure will allow to explain the mechanism of appearance of those or other deviations of property values from the expected ones.

Studying the structure of polymers by microscopic methods is an interesting and challenging task. The search for the relationship between the structure and properties of polymeric materials still remains an urgent problem of polymer science and has no universal solution. Electron microscopy occupies one of the most important places among the various microscopic methods of material research, mainly due to its high spatial resolution. The application of electron microscopy to study the surface structure of polymers allows opening up new ways to control the structure and, therefore, the properties of bodies, and allows solving the problem of obtaining materials with desired characteristics more effectively. In recent decades, electron microscopy has become the most important method for studying the structure and morphology of polymeric materials.

In this work, to study the surface morphology of the initial polymers and mixtures were carried out with a scanning electron microscope SEM - EVO MA 10 (Zeiss, Germany).

Fig. 1 shows electron micrographs of chips obtained with a scanning microscope from samples of SEVA, PVC-C and mixtures based on them in the ratio PVC-C:SEVA = 0.85:0.15.

Figure 1(a) shows microphotographs of ethylene vinyl acetate copolymer surface. The sample surface is shiny, which is typical for polyolefins. The copolymer surface is not homogeneous. It can be assumed that the non-uniformity of the

structure is associated with the formation of a crystalline supramolecular structure, which is characteristic of polyethylene (PE content in the copolymer is 82%).

Fig. 1 (b) shows microphotographs of polyvinyl chloride suspension surface. The surface of the sample is matte, greasy due to the plasticizer. White inclusions in the microphotographs presumably belong to emulsifiers used in PVC-C synthesis.

Figure 1. Scanning electron microscopy micrographs:

a - copolymer of ethylene with vinyl acetate (SEVA-18); b - polyvinyl chloride suspension;

Thus, characterizing the morphology of the structure of polymer mixtures, we can conclude that in this system the suspension polyvinyl chloride is fundamental, which determines the basic deformation and strength properties of the mixture. In the process of mixing a certain ratio of copolymer and thermoplastic, two-phase systems are formed, i. e. mechanical mixtures of technologically compatible polymers with very close values of solubility parameters are formed.

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